

The challenges and possibilities of real-time Wave Field Synthesis

Miguel Negrão

May, 2010

miguel.negrao@friendlyvirus.org

This paper describes an implementation of real-time spatialization using Wave Field Synthesis in the SuperCollider audio synthesis programming language. The basic theory of WFS is introduced, followed by the details of a new implementation of general SuperCollider real-time usage for the Wave Field Synthesis system of the Game of Life Foundation (WFS-GOL).

An application of the system using spatialized sine wave generators is described.

1 Wave Field Synthesis

Wave Field Synthesis is a sound spatialization technique that aims at the complete duplication of the original sound field and therefore, at its core, it does not rely on psychoacoustic effects, it relies instead “on the theoretical result that each physical sound field can be reconstructed from a distribution of secondary sources on a closed surface that surround the listeners. These secondary sources consist of distributions of monopoles and dipoles.” (Boone & Verheijen, 1998). The theoretical foundation uses the Kirchhoff-Helmholtz integral: If S is a surface surrounding a listener at position r , then sound pressure at that point in the frequency domain is

$$P(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \iint_S \left[P(\mathbf{r}_s, \omega) \frac{\partial}{\partial n} \left(\frac{e^{-jk|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s|}}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s|} \right) - \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{r}_s, \omega)}{\partial n} \frac{e^{-jk|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s|}}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s|} \right] dS.$$

In the time domain and considering a finite, discrete array of sources the expression will become a finite sum of delayed versions of the pressure waves at the location of those sources, multiplied by an amplitude coefficient.

The use of truncated discrete arrays introduces errors in the reproduction of the sound field. The fact that an array is made of discrete loudspeakers means that it cannot

reproduce the spatial characteristics of waves with higher frequencies than the spatial sampling frequency $f_s = \frac{c}{2D}$ where D is the distance between speakers (Daniel, Nicol, & Moreau, 2003). For an actual WFS array this frequency is usually around 1000Hz, nevertheless this “can be regarded as good enough quality, since low-frequency ITD cues which are important cues in spatial hearing, are then produced accurately” (Pulkki, 2001).

The WFS system has a couple of unique characteristics among spatialization systems. One of the most interesting aspects of WFS is that the sound field is correctly recreated in almost the whole area encompassed by the speakers (nearer than about 1 meter from the speakers, spatial distortion occurs). Instead of having a sweet spot, WFS has a “sweet area” where a fairly large audience can be placed and still perceive correctly the spatialization of the sounds. Another unique characteristic is that when one moves inside the listening area defined by the speaker rows, sources remain stationary and it’s therefore possible to walk “between” sources, or to, approach different zones of the sound field, thus enabling multiple perspectives of the sound stage (ambisonics for instance, only keeps angles constant and not actual positions).

In the theory of WFS the virtual sources to be reproduced are supposed to be outside the surface S for the Kirchhoff-Helmholtz integral conditions to hold. Nevertheless it is possible to reproduce virtual sources inside the surface S by using the time-reversal principle: “a converging wave field is essentially a time-reversed diverging one. One proceeds as follows: First, a virtual source is created at the position of the intended focused source but its radiated wave field is recreated behind the loudspeaker array [...]. Then, the loudspeaker driving functions are time reversed. This results in a wave field that converges towards the location of the virtual source and then diverges and makes up the desired wave field” (Ahrens & Spors, 2008). These sources are called *focused* virtual sources.

Nevertheless, focused sources cannot be rendered correctly for listeners in all sections of the listening area: “In order to evoke the perception of a virtual source inside the listening area, a wave field converging towards a focus point can be reproduced. As a consequence of causality, the wave field diverges after having passed the focus point [...]. A listener positioned in the diverging part of the wave field perceives a virtual source at the position of the focus point. A listener positioned in the converging part of the wave field will experience of confusing perception due to contradictory localization cues. Note that it is not possible to focus a wave field such that it exclusively diverges in a volume greater than one half-space. The boundary of this half-space includes the position of the focus point” (Ahrens & Spors, 2008).

Figure 1.1: WFS rendering of a monochromatic virtual source placed behind a line speaker array.

Figure 1.2: WFS rendering of a focused source. View of the wave fronts diverging from the focus point.

2 Real-Time Wave Field Synthesis: RT_WFS Library

The original software of the WFS-GOL¹, developed by Wouter Snoei and Raviv Ganchrow, allows the user to play mono sound files from disk and to attach a trajectory to each file. The software provides a GUI to control the start times, fade times, trajectories, etc. Since the system is quite recent (2006) and still in development, it did not allow at this time (early 2010) for real-time control of the trajectories or to use the custom SC SynthDefs instead of just mono files. Because I was interested in the possibilities of using the system by playing synths in real-time and panning them through the WFS panners, I started implementing a library for this end.

The essential problem of the WFS-GOL system is that it uses two discrete computers to compute the WFS panning for each source. Since the rendering of the output for all the 192 channels is quite CPU heavy, two different computers were needed, each one computing the output of half of the array (96 speakers). WFS needs absolute accuracy of timing of the delays for each speaker in order to successfully recreate the wave field, it thus becomes necessary to correctly synchronize the two computers so that their output is aligned in time with a resolution at the sample level. The current implementation of the system uses a master laptop that outputs a constant click signal through digital optical connections to each of the two slave computers. This system works well to play a fixed score, whose events are known in advance, but was not suitable for real-time operation.

To solve this issue, a new framework was started by Wouter Snoei which will in time become the WFS-GOL 2.0 software. Since version 2.0 was not yet available at the start of 2010, I started to implement my own slightly altered version of the software (RT_WFS) based on the v1.0 of WFS library, on the early sketches of Wouter Snoei² (`SyncCenter`) and on a customized version of SuperCollider (`sc sample_sched`) provided by Francisco Velazquez³. This custom version⁴ of SuperCollider allows scheduling of synths in the SuperCollider server with accuracy up to the sample level: all that is needed is to send a single impulse from the master computer to the servers, record the sample count since the each slave server was booted, and then calculate the appropriate sample number at which synths should be started (considering server boot to be $t=0$). I also used `SyncCenter`, a class by Wouter Snoei to simplify the syncing process with the rendering servers, to which I added a method (`getSchedulingSampleCount`) to schedule a bundle in the slave

¹This Wave Field Synthesis system is owned by the foundation The Game of Life, based in the Netherlands. Raviv Ganchrow was responsible for the hardware design and initial algorithm development, and Wouter Snoei with the assistance of Jan Trützschler von Falkenstein completed the software development. The project was initiated by Arther Sauer in collaboration with Erwin Roebroeks and Gosuin van Heeswijk. It consists of 192 individual speakers fed by 192 channels of discrete audio, controlled by two computers, each with an 8 core processor. Since the SCServer is not multi-processor aware at the moment, to use all the computing power of the computers 8 SCServers are running on each computer and being controller by a third computer.

²I'm very grateful for all the assistance that Wouter Snoei gave me, without whom this project would not have been possible.

³More know in the SuperCollider community as blackrain.

⁴This version has still not been merged to into the official version of SuperCollider.

Figure 2.1: Time graph of events

servers.

When `SyncCenter` sends an impulse to the slave servers, the listener synths receive the trigger and send an OSC message back to the master computer with two important values⁵:

- The sample block (or vector) count since the slave server was booted.
- The number of samples of offset relative to the beginning of the signal block being processed at the moment the impulse was received.

This information provides us the value of $s1$ (see 1). During the syncing procedure `SyncCenter` also receives the same information ($m1$) from the master server⁶. To schedule a new event we use the method `Server:listSendPosBundle(position,bundle)` (from `sample_sched`), where *position* is the sample count at which the bundle should be played in the server, counting in number of samples since the server was booted. This means that to schedule an event we need to know the value of $s3$. We can observe that, by definition, $s2 = m2$, because we want the event to happen at the same time in both servers. We have then

$$\begin{aligned}
 s3 &= s1 + s2 \\
 &= s1 + m2 \\
 &= s1 + m3 - m1
 \end{aligned}$$

We already know $s1$ and $m1$ (recorded previously) and we know $m3$ because `SyncCenter` is running in the same computer as the master and therefore has instantaneous access (for

⁵The values are provided by the UGen `BlockOffset.ar`

⁶From the master server, since it runs in the same computer as the language, it only receives the sample count offset (via `SampleOffset.ir`) within the signal block, since the block count can be obtained directly by calling `server.blockCount`.

the purpose of audio scheduling) to the sample count since the master server was booted (`server.blockCount`). `m3` will then be the sample count at the moment of scheduling plus a time delta (e.g. 1 one second, or some hundred of milliseconds, depending on network conditions) , which is a delay from the moment of issuing the scheduling of the bundle to allow for the OSC packet to arrive at destination. The code becomes:

```
*getSchedulingSampleCount{ |delta = 1, serverIndex = 0|
    ~(remoteCounts[serverIndex] +(((master.options.blockSize*
        master.blockCount) + (delta*master.sampleRate)) -
        masterCount))
}
```

Also, any synth played must use `OffsetOut.ar` as output to ensure that it is started with the correct sample offset in the current signal vector. Only one synth should use `OffsetOut.ar` in a signal chain where one synth is processing the output of another synth.

The final step needed for real-time operation is to allow the use of normal SC code with the system. All synths will be running in two computers at the same time, started at exactly the same time (at exactly the same sample), and they must output the exact same signal on both computers. This means that all synthdefs must have a specific random seed that is the same for both computers, in such a way that the random generators will output the same signal on both computers. In the same way all busses, buffers and groups have to be created in the same way in both computers.

To make it easier to use the system, and to avoid having to explicitly construct two sets of synths, groups, buffers, and busses, for each slave server, I created the Cluster library, which essentially holds an array of items and delegates any method calls sent to it to all the elements in the array, thus fooling SuperCollider into thinking that an array of servers is just one server, an array of synths is just one synth, etc. The library consists of classes that substitute all the objects representing elements of the SuperCollider server: `ClusterServer`, `ClusterSynth`, `ClusterSynthDef`, `ClusterBus`, `ClusterGroup`, `ClusterRootNode`, `ClusterBuffer`, `ClusterOSCBundle`, `ClusterMonitor`. Any existing SuperCollider code can be ported to the WFS system by changing the normal SuperCollider objects to their Cluster versions.

Example of Cluster library usage

```
~server = ClusterServer([
    Server("slave1",NetAddr("127.0.0.1", 53177),~options).boot
    .makeWindow,
    Server("slave2",NetAddr("127.0.0.1", 53178),~options).boot
    .makeWindow]);

~group = ClusterGroup(~server);
~bus = ClusterBus.audio(~server,1)
~synth = ClusterSynth(\test,target: ~group)
```

The cluster classes work by overriding the `doesNotUnderstand` method. All cluster classes inherit from `ClusterBasic`, and contain only the variable `items` which is an array containing the various objects (synths, groups, etc). When a cluster class receives a

call to a method, since it doesn't have any methods explicitly defined, this will cause the `doesNotUnderstand` method from `ClusterBasic` to be called. This method will check which normal SC class does this cluster class represent (e.g. `ClusterSynth` represents `Synth`) and then will check if the method called exists in the represented class or in any of its parent classes. If so, it then loops through all elements in `items` calling the method with the given arguments. The methods that the represented class has overloaded from `Object` are manually implemented to forward to `doesNotUnderstand`, since otherwise those methods would be caught by `Object`. The arguments of the methods called on the cluster classes can be of three types:

- Normal SC objects, such as numbers, in which case they are just duplicated and passed to each object in `items`.
- A special type of class, `ClusterArg` (e.g. `ClusterArg([100,200])`), in which case they can have separate values for each element in `items`. All the arguments are recursively expanded, since one of the arguments can be an array containing a `ClusterArg` object (e.g. `[2,35,1.0,ClusterArg([100,200])`).
- Other Cluster objects (e.g. `ClusterBus.audio(ClusterServer([~server1,~server2]),1)`)

There are also two classes to control the syncing procedure: `RT_WFS_Client` and `RT_WFS_Center`.

- `RT_WFS_Client`: This class is used in the two server computers, and it creates the 8 servers (one per core) and the appropriate synthdefs for WFS panning, which are slightly altered copies of the ones in the WFS 1.0 library. It is run automatically when `SuperCollider` starts.
- `RT_WFS_Center`: this class is called in the master computer to initialize control of the two server computers, and to sync with them. After syncing has been successful, this class is responsible for scheduling bundles to each slave server (`RT_WFS_Center.sendClusterBundle(clusterBundle, serverNum, delay)`).

Finally there is a class for panning: `WFSPanner(bus, type)`. This class creates a synth that the user can place after their own synths in the node tree, and using a private bus, route the audio from the main synth to the `WFSPanner`, it then outputs the 96 channels of audio necessary for WFS operation. `WFSPanner`'s position is controlled from the language via `: myWFSPanner.move(x, y)`.

Other than syncing in the beginning of a session, and using the Cluster classes, the WFS system can be used in very much the same way as in normal `SuperCollider` usage, allowing for dynamic creation and panning of synths, something which is quite difficult in a WFS system which is only interfaceable via fixed audio inputs and OSC messages.

3 Sine Field

3.1 Concept

The SineField system aims at the precise exploration of the harmonic spectrum, by controlling the level and location in space of each individual frequency of the spectrum. Sine waves, being the “building blocks” of pitched sounds⁷, allow to construct an arbitrarily defined harmonic spectrum. It was interesting to explore what happens when this additive synthesis does not come out in just one spatial location, but each individual harmonic is placed in a specific location in space.

The idea is to place combinations of sine waves at specific locations in space, with frequencies very close together thus producing beats that happen both in time and in space. A scalar field is mapped to the frequency of the sine waves, in such a way that the position (x, y) of the sine wave in space determines its frequency by a certain function $f(x, y)$. This frequency field is kept static and the sine waves are free to roam through it, location and frequency become bound to each other, and any evolution in the frequency space will have repercussions in localization and vice-versa. The challenge is to design movements that yield interesting harmonic and spatial progressions at the same time.

Because the sine waves are difficult to localize their positions in space will not be clearly heard, instead each combination of frequencies and positions creates a kind of topology that is perceived by the listener as being different at every position in space. When listening to the output it is difficult to pin-point the exact location of the sine waves, yet, there is a very present sensation of spatiality, and sometimes the beats seem to occur along directions with the sound oscillating back and forth along a certain axis.

3.1.1 Formalization

The system consists of a scalar field $F : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a set $\Omega = \{p_1, \dots, p_N\}$ with $p_i = (x_i, y_i)$ of N points in the plane each one representing a sine wave oscillator. The scalar field is composed by summing Gaussian functions centered around the points $g_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$, more precisely,

$$F = k \sum_{i=1}^M a_i \Gamma_{g_i}$$

with

$$\Gamma_{g_i}(p) = e^{-\frac{\|p-g_i\|^2}{2\sigma^2}},$$

σ a constant and k a normalization constant such that the maximum value of F is 1.

The scalar field F maps points in the plane to values between 0 and 1, which are then scaled to an appropriate interval to be assigned to the frequency of the sine wave oscillators. If the frequency interval is $[a, b]$ then the scaling function is

$$s_{a,b}(x) = a + x(b - a).$$

⁷Sine waves are just one of many possible families of functions to use for decomposing signals, for instance, the Haar wavelet uses a square wave as building block. Sine waves are, though, a particularly good basis for the decomposition of pitched sounds.

Figure 3.1: An example of a scalar field used in the Sine Field system.

If p is a point in the plane, and the desired interval for frequencies is $[a, b]$ then the frequency of the sine wave oscillator at that location will be

$$f_p = s_{a,b}(F(p)).$$

The system is defined by choosing a set of frequencies $S = \{f_1, \dots, f_N\}$, a set of scalar fields $\{F_1, \dots, F_N\}$ and creating groups of sine wave oscillators $\{G_1, \dots, G_N\}$ whose frequencies are very close to the frequencies in S . If a sine wave oscillator belongs to G_i it will have frequency within a range $[f_i \frac{1}{d}, f_i d]$ where d is a deviation value. If this sine wave oscillator is located at point p then it's frequency will be $s_{f_i \frac{1}{d}, f_i d}(F_i(p))$.

4 Implementation

The Sine Field system was implemented in SuperCollider. A collection of classes to deal with scalar and vector fields was implemented and all the necessary operations were condensed in a single class SineField that represented one of the groups of sine wave oscillators.

The deviation value used was 1.05, so that if the center frequency of a group was, for example, 600Hz all the sine wave oscillators in that group would have frequencies in the range [571, 4, 630].

The center frequencies were determined from a starting frequency f by choosing some of it's harmonics and subharmonics. With n harmonics and m sub-harmonics the center frequency set S would be

$$S = \{m^{-1}f, \dots, 2^{-1}f, f, 2f, \dots, nf\}.$$

Figure 4.1: GUI for SineFieldGroup object.

A typical value for starting frequency was 303.96Hz and using up to 5 harmonic and sub-harmonic bands.

The scalar field F was produced by choosing 3 random points in the plane with coefficients a_i also randomly chosen, but normalized such that the biggest coefficient would always be 1. The groups of sine wave oscillators contained up to 4 sine wave oscillators per group, and were also attributed random positions in the plane (within a chosen radius).

A movement system was also implemented that would move the points from their starting position to the geometrical mean of the points within each group. If group G_i has sine wave oscillators with locations $\{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ then the points would move to location

$$p_{center} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i}{n}.$$

The closer the points are the closer their frequencies will be, since F is a continuous function. This means that as points are moving closer the beats are slowing down until becoming very long or non-perceptible.

The SineField class also has a method `.spawn` that will select new random positions for the points and crossfade to the new positions, by creating new synths and freeing the old ones⁸.

⁸If the position is simply changed within WFSpanner synth this will cause a click due to the instantaneous change of the delays that are used for the WFS panning.

4.0.2 Performance

The Sine Field system was used in a performance using the WFS-GOL system in March 2010. It was used at that time in conjunction with another of my projects, the SuperStrings system, that features drones produced by spatialized string physical models. Usually one group of sine wave oscillators was introduced over the already playing strings, then slowly more groups of sine wave oscillators joined. Since the strings produce a continuous sound mass the sine waves would seem to merge with the partials of the strings and also at times modulate the sound of the strings. In the performance the strings would then be faded out and the rest of the groups of sine waves would be introduced and the movement of the sine waves would begin, with the sine waves converging to one point for each group. The performance would end when the beats were very slow or imperceptible. The range in which harmonics were varying due to the movement of the sine wave generators in space (due to the coupling given by the scalar field) was quite small (less than a semitone), so that what resulted were not glissandi from one chord to another chord, but just different beat frequencies and spatial patterns.

For future performance I have been exploring several ideas:

To use scalar fields of the same type as the ones used for the frequency, to control the amplitude of each group of sine waves. To do so, one “slice”⁹ of the field is taken, giving an envelope which is then connected to the level of the sine wave group. By taking several different “slices” of the field and assigning them to each group the harmonic spectrum can be made to slowly and continuously evolve, always maintaining the same pitch structure, just changing the emphasis of each harmonic.

To use sine wave groups with very high frequencies (for instance 5000Hz, 7000Hz and 10000Hz). In this frequency range, the beats are so fast that they become timbres, similar to crickets sounds. For these frequency ranges, I periodically select new random positions for the sine waves, creating successive spatial and timbric patterns.

The SineField system allowed me to explore the most basic constituents of continuous spatial tones (sine waves, their levels, frequencies, positions in space and frequency relations) and, even despite the simplicity of the material, very interesting textures and evolving patterns were produced.

References

- Ahrens, J., & Spors, S. (2008). Notes on rendering focused directional virtual sound sources in wave field synthesis. *Tagung der Deutschen Akustischen Gesellschaft, Dresden, March 10th-13th*.
- Boone, M., & Verheijen, E. (1998, Jan). Sound reproduction applications with wave field synthesis. *PREPRINTS-AUDIO ENGINEERING SOCIETY*. Available from <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=8491>

⁹If the field is $f(x, y)$ then a slice would be $\{f(x, y) : x, y \in \mathbb{R}, y = ax + b\}$, that is, the intersection of a vertical plane with the surface defined by the field.

- Daniel, J., Nicol, R., & Moreau, S. (2003). Further investigations of high order ambisonics and wavefield synthesis for holophonic sound imaging. *PREPRINTS-AUDIO ENGINEERING SOCIETY*.
- Pulkki, V. (2001). Spatial sound generation and perception by amplitude panning techniques. *Report, 62*, 1456–6303.